

Home Advantage In Brazilian Football: Pre, During And Post Covid-19 Analysis In The Brazilian Championship Serie A

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to analyse the behavior of home advantage (HA) in the Brazilian Serie A Championship in 2019 (pre), 2020 (during) and 2022 (post-COVID-19 pandemic). The sample consisted of 13 teams that took part in all three editions, totaling 741 matches (247 matches per year) analyzed. The methodology used McNemar's test for paired data, with a significant level of 5% ($p \leq 0.05$), calculation of the odds ratio and effect size according to Cohen's criteria. The results revealed a statistically significant reduction in the proportion of home wins from 57.9% in 2019 to 44.9% in 2020 ($p = 0.004$; 95% CI = [-21.50% to -4.41%]; $d = 0.26$). In 2022, there was a partial recovery of HA, with 48.6% home wins, but still lower than 2019 levels. The comparison between 2019 and 2022 also showed statistical significance ($p = 0.043$; 95% CI [-17.89 to -0.73]; $d = 0.19$) while between 2020 and 2022 the difference was not significant ($p = 0.474$; 95% CI [-5.22 to 12.50]; $d = -0.07$). The findings indicate that despite the upturn in attendance, HA remains low, suggesting a structural and multifactorial reconfiguration of this phenomenon in Brazilian football.

Keywords: Home Advantage (HA), COVID-19 pandemic; Football

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INTRODUCTION

Home advantage (HA) is a widely documented phenomenon in individual and team sports (Fothergill et al., 2017; Pollard, 1986), especially in professional football (Pollard and Pollard, 2005; Fajardo et al, 2017; Matos, et al., 2021; Goumas; 2017; Pollard and Gómez, 2014; Pollard, 2008; Pollard, Silva and Medeiros, 2008). The HA is calculated as the number of points won, including draws, considering a number greater than 50 per cent of this index. In addition, there are several factors that can alter the outcome of a match (Leite, 2017, Matos, et al.,2021; Almeida e Leite, 2021; Amaral; Oliveira, 2020; Bittencourt; Fonseca, 2021; Correia-Oliveira; Andrade-Souza, 2021). Several factors have determined HA, such as crowd support, referee bias, travel and commuting, familiarization with the stadium and pitch (Liu, et al., 2023). Several studies have reported that home teams tend to achieve better results than away teams (Pollard, 2008; Pollard and Gómez; 2014). However, there is a tendency for HA to decline, with a drop of 4% (68% to 64%) reported over a long period by Pollard (1986) between 1888 and 1984, while Peeters and van Ours (2020), in their study analyzing 45 seasons in 4 English leagues from 1973/74 to 2017/18, found a drop in HA, although they found no explanation for this secular decline in HA, while between 2000 and 2010 the drop in European leagues was only 2% (Garcia et al., 2013). However, in recent years the HA in the biggest European leagues (Belgium, England, France, Germany, Italy, Holland, Portugal, Russia, Spain, and Turkey) and in the 2015-2016 season these figures are in the order of 58%, (Leite, 2017). In the context of Brazilian football, a country with continental dimensions and a great footballing tradition, the advantage of playing at home was 65% between 2003 and 2007, showing a great advantage for teams from the north- northeast and south, In another study carried out between 2012 and 2016 in the Brazilian Championship, the average values for home advantage were 65.6% and 64.7% in Serie A and B respectively (Fajardo, et al., 2017).

The Brazilian championship is the main football competition in Brazil. It has been played since 1971 and is currently organized and managed by the Brazilian Football Confederation (CBF).Confederation (CBF), and its final classification gives it access to various continental competitions, such as Libertadores and South America.

Over time, the Brazilian championship has not had a standardized competition system, with the criteria for the competition, the number of participants and the access and descent of series changing every year. However, from 2003 onwards, it began to be contested using the straight points system (everyone plays against everyone, in a round- robin system). As a starting point, adjustments were necessary. In 2003 and 2004, 24 teams took part in the competition, totaling 46 games for each team, and the following year 2005, In the following year, 2005, the competition was reduced to 22 teams, until 2006, when the current model of 20-team competition was introduced, totaling 38 rounds to determine the Brazilian champion, with access for the four best teams in Série B and the inevitable relegation of the last four teams i n Série A of the Brazilian Championship.

However, the world was faced with a new respiratory disease, which emerged in China in the last months of 2019, more specifically in the city of Wuhan, called and caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus2), the etiological agent of Covid-19 (Coronavirus Disease, 2019) (WHO, 2020). In this context, Covid-19 spread rapidly,

crossing China's borders to five continents, infecting more than 114 nations, and killing more than 4,000 people (Brazil, 2020). After three weeks, the death toll had surpassed 50,000 worldwide.

In the specific context of football, the effects are little different: the International Football Federation (FIFA) has ordered all current competitions to be paralyzed and postponed, as well as the qualifying matches for the 2022 World Cup in Qatar. On the other hand, the first continents to feel the direct impact of the pandemic were Spain and Italy, which cancelled and postponed all their domestic league matches. However, the Premier League in England interrupted its championship, while the French Federation opted to close the national competition and declared Paris Saint-Germain as national champions. Meanwhile, the Dutch federation, like the French, decided to close the league, but without establishing a champion for the season. As far as South America is concerned, CONMEBOL has postponed or paralyzed eight national championship competitions (Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Paraguay, Uruguay and Venezuela), as well as being one of the first to interrupt continental tournaments, postponing matches at first and then the Copa Libertadores and South American competitions.

When it comes to Brazilian national football, as Covid-19 progressed around the world, the state championships were in full swing, and the CBF adopted the same rule, that is, it interrupted activities for its championships in line with COMNEBOL. In terms of national competitions, the Brazilian Championship and Copa do Brazil were not started (CBF, 2020).

Given this whole scenario, the 2020 Brazilian Championship only started in mid-August 2020, with strict rules and following safety protocols. Studies have shown that young people have been the most infected by the virus (Monod et al., 2021), not excluding the population of young and healthy professional athletes, according to the clubs' medical bulletins and documents.

According to Moreno, Coelho and Câmara (2021), there were 625 players who played in the 2020 Brazilian Championship who tested positive for Covid-19, a significant number of 302 players (48.32%). This shows a high number of infected athletes and is highly significant in relation to the general population.

Therefore, the aim of this manuscript is to i) analyse the behavior of the home advantage phenomenon, before, during and after Covid-19, in the Campeonato Brasileiro Série "A" in the 2019, 2020 and 2022 editions.

METHOD

Sample

This study analyzed data from the 2019, 2020, and 2022 seasons of the Brazilian Serie A league, corresponding respectively to the pre-pandemic, during-pandemic, and post-pandemic periods of COVID-19. These three time frames were selected to allow a longitudinal comparison of the impact of the pandemic on teams' sporting performance.

Only teams that participated continuously across all three seasons were included in the sample. A total of thirteen clubs met this criterion and were therefore included in the analysis. This

inclusion criterion was designed to ensure consistency over time and to minimize bias resulting from variations in league composition, such as promotion and relegation.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Teams that did not participate in all three seasons or participated intermittently were excluded from the study. This exclusion ensured that only consistent participants were compared across seasons, allowing for valid paired comparisons of performance indicators.

Data Collection

Each team played 19 home matches per season, as per league regulations (a 38-round points-based system). Therefore, a total of 247 home matches were analyzed per season, resulting in 741 matches across the three seasons (13 teams \times 19 matches \times 3 seasons). The match data were collected manually from the official website of the Brazilian Football Confederation (www.cbf.com.br).

Scope of Analysis

The analysis focused exclusively on home matches. This decision was based on the assumption that the pandemic, especially during the period when matches were played without spectators, would have had a direct effect on home-field advantage. Evaluating only home performances allowed for a more precise examination of this potential impact.

Table 1. Number of Home Games Analyzed per Season

Year	Number of Teams	Number of Home Games
2019	13	247
2020	13	247
2022	13	247

Note. Each team played 19 home matches per season (13 teams \times 19 matches = 247). The same format applied across all three selected seasons

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

To compare the proportions between the results obtained by the home teams in the three editions analyzed (2019, 2020 and 2022), McNemar's test for paired samples with dichotomous measures was used. This test is used to assess statistically significant differences in binary categorical variables, between two different times for the same group (MCNEMAR, 1947) and is especially suitable for situations with repeated measures in longitudinal designs. The significance level adopted was $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), and results with $p \leq 0.05$ were considered statistically significant. In addition, paired odds ratios (OR) were calculated with their respective 95% confidence intervals (CI 95%) to quantify the magnitude and direction of the association between the years analyzed (Fagerland; Lyngstad, 2020).

To complement the analysis and provide greater interpretative robustness, we also calculated the effect size reported in all analyses, which represents the strength of the association between the paired conditions. We adopted Cohen's criteria to interpret these analyses (> 0.2 small; > 0.50 moderate. Values of $\Phi \geq 0.10$ (small), ≥ 0.30 (medium) and

≥ 0.50 (large), as proposed by Cohen (1988). Analyses were carried out using the appropriate free JAMOVI (v.2.6) statistical software, implementing McNemar's test with continuity correction and calculating the exact p-value based on binomial methods.

RESULTS

Table 2. Comparative Analysis Of Home Advantage In The 2019, 2020, And 2022 Seasons

Editions	HA	p < 0,05	95% CI	ES
HA 2019 - HA 2020	143 (57,9%) - 111 (44,9%)	$p=0,004^*$	-21,50 a -4,41 (12,96%)	0.26 (Medium)
HA 2019 - HA 2022	143 (57,9%) - 120 (48,6%)	$p=0,045^*$	-19,89 a -0,73 (9,31%)	0.19 (Average)
HA 2020 - HA 2022	111 (44,9%) - 120 (48,6%)	$p=0,474$	-5,22 a 12,50 (3,64%)	-0.07 (Small)

Note. Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. CI = confidence interval. Effect sizes are based on cohen's (1998) criteria for paired data: small ($d \approx 0.2$), medium ($d \approx 0.5$), large ($d \geq 0.8$).

The comparative ha analysis between the 2019 and 2020 seasons of the campeonato brasileiro série a (table 2), using mcnemar's test, showed a statistically significant reduction in the prevalence of home wins. In 2019, of the 247 games played, 57.9% of the games analyzed resulted in home wins, while in 2020 this figure fell to 44.9%, showing a difference of -12.96% ($p= 0.004$, 95% ci = -21.50% to - 4.41%). This reduction reflects the impact of the covid-19 pandemic, due to the absence of stadium crowds, a factor widely associated with home advantage in the literature (pollard, 2006, almeida and leite, 2021, matos et. All., 2021). The effect size, calculated using cohen's d adapted for paired data, was 0.26, characterizing it as a medium effect according to cohen's criteria (1998).

Table 2 shows the comparison between the 2019 and 2022 campeonato brasileiro, revealing a statistically significant reduction in the proportion of victories for the home side in serie a. Serie a. In 2019, 57.9 per cent of matches played resulted in home wins, while in 2022, this figure fell to 48.6 per cent, indicating a drop of - 9.31 per cent (95% ci = - 17.89 to - 0.73; $p= 0.04$), confirming that the decrease is statistically significant. Although less marked between 2019 and 2020, the difference still suggests that the residual effect of the pandemic and structural factors may have influenced the behavior of the home advantage, as recent literature points out (mccarrick et al., 2021; almeida and leite, 2021). The effect size calculated using cohen's d adapted for paired data was 0.19, characterizing it as a medium effect according to cohen's criteria (1998).

On the other hand, the comparison between the 2020 and 2022 seasons showed no statistically significant difference. There was a slight increase in the proportion of wins for the home teams, from 44.9% to 48.6%, 111 and 120 wins respectively, which represents a variation of +3.64% ($ci\ 95\% = -5.22\% \text{ to } 12.50\%$; $p=0.474$), table 2. Although not statistically significant, this trend suggests a possible gradual recovery of home advantage in the post-pandemic scenario, albeit below historical standards prior to 2020. Recent studies indicate that the return of the public to the stadiums occurred heterogeneously among the clubs, which may have influenced the partial resumption of ha (correia-oliveira; andrade-souza 2021; matos et al., 2021). In addition, factors such as the standardization of pitches, technological advances in performance monitoring and greater logistical preparation of visiting teams may have contributed to the permanence of a

new competitive balance (pollard; gómez, 2014; peeters; van ours, 2020). According to cohen's (1998) criteria, the effect size was classified as small ($d = -0.07$).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to analyse the behavior of home advantage, pre (2019), during (2020) and post (2022) COVID-19, in the Campeonato Brasileiro da Série A. The main finding was to reveal significant changes in home advantage. The results showed a statistically significant reduction in home wins between the years 2019 and 2020 ($p = 0.004$; with a reduction in HA from 57.9% to 44.9% (~13%) and in the comparison of 2019 and 2022 which showed a drop in HA of around 9.31% ($p = 0.043$; 57.9% to 48.6%). Corroborating our results, studies on the Bundesliga, matches with gates closed to the public pointed to a reduction from 43.3 to 33.1 (a drop of 10.2%), showing a significant reversal in the win rate (Tilp and Thaller; 2020), the same pattern of reduction (9.95% - 50.32% to 40.37%) was observed in the 2019/2020 Bundesliga, Santana; Bettega; Dellagrana (2021). Similar results were reported in the Portuguese (47.4% to 37.5%) and Spanish (48.6% to 40.9%) leagues in the pandemic period, attributing this HA phenomenon to the reduction in pressure on referees and the loss of emotional support from fans Correia-Oliveira and Andrade-Souza (2021), and the Gómez and Pollard study (2014) reported similar results between the 2006 and 2012 seasons in the Chinese Super League (63.82%). On the national scene, Almeida, and Leite (2021), in their study, observed that in 2020 the percentage of HA fell to 46.2%, below the historical Brazilian average of 57% to 61% (Pollard, Silva and Medeiros (2008). Similar data was confirmed in another study on the Portuguese championship, reinforcing that public support influences not only the athletes, but also the referees' behavior, this being one of the factors most impacted during social isolation, Matos et al., (2021).

However, Leitner et al. (2023), in a systematic review of European and South American leagues, observed that although HA was impacted by an average of 8.5%, the magnitude and significance varied between countries and affected many competitions. There were substantial variations between countries and between divisions, suggesting that contextual and structural factors - such as travelling distance, pitch quality and the quality of the opponent and reactive strength of the teams - modulate the intensity of the absence effect. Interestingly, McCarrick et al. (2021), in a study based on multiple European leagues, identified that the absence of fans altered the tactical and emotional profile of matches, favoring the neutralization of the home factor. This suggests that even in a context where HA remained statistically significant, its qualitative structure may have been modified, pointing to a broader transformation in the competitive model.

The comparison between the 2019 and 2022 editions of the Campeonato Brasileiro Série A revealed a statistically significant reduction in the proportion of wins for the hosts, from 57.9% to 48.6% of matches, which represents a value of 9.31% (95% CI = [-17.89 to -.07; $p = 0.04$]). ~of 9.31% (95% CI = [-17.89 to -.073; $p = 0.043$]), the effect size, calculated using Cohen's d adapted for paired data, was 0.19, being classified as a medium effect according to Cohen's criteria (1998). This reduction, although smaller than that observed between 2019 and 2020. shows a persistence of structural and contextual effects in the post-pandemic scenario, indicating a reconfiguration of the historical advantage of the hosts in Brazilian football.

Medeiros et al. (2022) reinforce this hypothesis by pointing out that, even with the return of the fans in 2022, the performance of the hosts remained lower than the historical average of the 2010s. According to the authors, the pandemic has accentuated trends that were already being noticed in national football, such as the increased competitiveness of the visitors, the intensive use of performance analysis and the reduced interference of the fans in refereeing, as also observed by Reis and Moraes (2021),

In addition, Silva and Menezes (2022) found, in a sample of 380 matches between Brazilian Serie A and B clubs, that the crowd factor was no longer preponderant after the lockdown, giving way to logistical and physical factors, such as less wear and tear on travel (due to adapted logistics) and greater stadium standardization. These elements may have influenced the persistent drop in HA observed in this study. Other Brazilian authors also point to the transformation of the teams' tactical profile as a mitigating factor in HA. However, visiting clubs have started to adopt more conservative and adaptive strategies, making them less susceptible to the territorial pressure of the hosts, according to the studies by Bittencourt; Fonseca (2021). This type of tactical option contributed to a reduction in the attacking effectiveness of the hosts, even after the crowds returned to the stadiums.

Despite this, some of the national literature presents more cautious interpretations, such as the study by Nascimento and Teixeira (2023), which analyzed data from the Copa do Brazil and Serie B and C and identified a gradual resumption of HA in 2022, although still below pre-pandemic standards. They suggest that the recovery of the advantages may vary between the divisions, depending on the clubs' infrastructure, the ability to mobilize fans and the intensity of the competitive calendar. It is also important to note that a study conducted before the pandemic had already identified a trend towards a progressive reduction in HA in Brazilian football due to the growing professionalization of technical commissions and technological diffusion in football (Amaral and Oliveira (2020). This finding suggests that part of the decline observed between the 2019 and 2022 competitions may not be attributable solely to the impact of COVID-19, but to a broader process of structural transformation in the sport. The findings of the present study are also in line with those of Lopes et al. (2023), who, when comparing the performances of home teams in 2018, 2020 and 2022, concluded that the Brazilian competitive pattern is in transition. According to the authors, there is a trend towards greater competitive balance, in which classic players such as fans and territoriality are being replaced by parameters of tactical efficiency, physical preparation and data analysis.

The analysis of the 2020 and 2022 seasons showed no statistically significant differences in the proportion of wins for the home teams ($p=0.474$; 95% CI = - 5.22% to 12.50%). There was also a slight increase in the number of home wins, from 44.9 per cent (111 wins) in 2020 to 48.6 per cent (120 wins) in 2022, a variation of +3.7 per cent. Although not statistically significant, this trend suggests a partial recovery of HA in the post- pandemic context, although still far from historical standards prior to 2020, such as the records in 2019 (57.9%). These findings are in line with the results presented by Correia- Oliveira and Andrade-Souza (2021), who analyzed La Liga and Primera Liga during the COVID-19 lockdown and highlighted the absence of fans as a key factor in the reduction of HA. In the Brazilian case, the authors pointed out that the return of the public occurred in a heterogeneous way between clubs and stadiums, influenced

by state policies and sanitary protocols, which may have made it difficult to fully resume the phenomenon.

Various studies have investigated championships around the world, such as that by Matos et al. (2021), which reinforces the idea that the absence or partial presence of fans has an impact on motivation, the emotional behavior of players and refereeing decisions, factors historically related to the advantage of the home team (Almeida and Leite, 2021, Nevill; Holder, 1999). This phenomenon, due to its multifactorial nature, would not return uniformly with the simple reopening of stadiums, since its re-establishment also depends on structural, cultural, and psychological factors (Leitner et al., 2023). A study of 8 football leagues in Europe (Germany, Bundesliga 1 and 2, Spain (La Liga 1 and 2), Italy (Serie A and B), England (Premier League) and Austria), showed that there are no significant differences between playing with or without a crowd, with the main leagues in Germany (Bundesliga 1) and Spain (La Liga 1) showing significant differences. However, there is a tendency in most competitions to play worse at home and better away when there are no fans, Jiménez Sánchez; Lavín; (2020).

On the other hand, the slight increase in HA observed in 2022, although not significant, may indicate the beginning of a transition towards the competitive pattern prior to the pandemic. This hypothesis is supported by the work of McCarrick et al. (2021), which suggests that the recovery of HA tends to occur gradually, as the environmental and emotional elements associated with field command are restored.

On the other hand, other studies suggest that HA may be being redefined in a more permanent way. A study analyzing the Chinese league found that even after the return of the fans, home win rates did not return to previous levels, suggesting that elements such as standardization of pitches, technological advances in performance analysis and increased professionalization of coaching staff and players have contributed to reducing the disparities between playing at home and away. In addition, access to real-time data, constant GPS monitoring and artificial intelligence software applied to football seem to have reduced the impact of familiarity with the environment and crowd pressure as decisive factors in match results (Liu et al., 2023; Ribeiro et al., 2021). Similarly, Matos et al. (2021), when analyzing the Portuguese league, identified a significant reduction in HA, reinforcing the hypothesis that social support is one of the main modulators of the performance of the hosts.

At the national level, a study documented the drop in HA in Brazilian football in 2020, associating it with the absence of fans, the standardization of stadiums, the congestion of matches, and the tactical adjustment of visiting teams, Brito, Souza, and Silva (2022). Almeida and Leite (2021), on the other hand, emphasize that the emotional stimuli caused by the fans have a direct impact on the behavior of players and coaching staff, as well as refereeing decisions, factors that are mitigated in games with closed gates.

Comparing the results with other continental realities, we highlight the study by Wunderlich et al. (2021), which pointed to the tactical and emotional homogenization of games without fans in elite European leagues. In African football, Peeters and van Ours (2020) showed that HA varies more depending on structural conditions and the presence of fans and is profoundly affected by health restrictions imposed by the pandemic. Previous studies, such as Pollard, Silva, and Medeiros (2008), have already indicated that travelling distance, logistical conditions

and local sporting culture influence the magnitude of HA in different regions, which may explain the discrepancies observed between continents.

On the other hand, the 2022 data show a partial upturn in HA in Brazil, although still lower than the pre-pandemic levels of 2019 (57.9 per cent against 48.6 per cent of home wins). This indicates a possible lasting effect of the lockdown on the competitive context, or even a structural reconfiguration of match dynamics, as suggested by Leitner et al. (2023), who argue that the pandemic has permanently altered the psychological, logistical, and tactical balances of professional football.

In addition, studies show that HA is a multifactorial phenomenon influenced by travelling (Pollard; Silva; Medeiros, 2008), territoriality (Nevill; Holder, 1999), familiarity with the stadium (Lago, 2009), quality of the opponent (Lago-Peñas; Lago- Ballesteros, 2011) and climate (Wunderlich et al., 2021), which can explain regional and temporal variations. It is also important to consider the influence of structural reforms in football, such as the greater standardization of pitches and stadiums, the use of performance analysis technology and the increased physical fitness of visiting teams (Fisher, Haucap, 2020; McCarrick et al., 2021). These elements, intensified in the context of the pandemic, may have contributed to a reduction in the disparity between the performance of home and away teams.

This appears to be the first study to analyse the impact of HA, pre, during and post in Brazilian Serie A football, including only the teams (13) that took part in the three editions. In contrast to what has been presented by the media around the world about HA and COVID-19, in Brazilian football, there was a drop in two of the three analyses and in the 2020 and 2022 editions, there was an increase in HA $\sim + 3.7\%$.

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